

OPTIMISATION OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PURULENT-NECROTIC COMPLICATIONS OF DIABETIC FOOT SYNDROME

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Relevance. According to WHO, "...much has been achieved worldwide in the treatment of diabetic foot syndrome (DFS), multidisciplinary approaches to treatment have been developed ..." [9]. [5, 9]. However, despite all the achievements, the number of leg amputations for purulent-necrotic complications of Diabetic Foot Syndrome is increasing, with "every hour in the world 55 diabetic patients lose a lower limb, which in turn is accompanied by a high mortality rate, treatment and rehabilitation costs ..." [4, 7]. In the world practice, scientific studies are conducted to develop new approaches to determining the optimal level of lower limb truncation in severe purulent-necrotic complications of DFS, which could not only save the lives of patients, but also create favourable conditions for healing of the amputation stump and early rehabilitation of this category of patients [1, 2, 6, 8]. At the same time, it is of particular importance to assess the viability of the lower limb tissues at the level of which amputation is planned to be performed in order to prevent purulent-necrotic complications from the amputation stump, which in most cases leads to reamputation at best, and at worst, to the development of systemic inflammatory response syndrome, as well as multi-organ dysfunction with lethal outcome [3, 5, 10].

Purpose of the study. Improving the results of complex surgical treatment of patients with purulent-necrotic complications of diabetic foot syndrome by optimising the methods of determining the proper level of amputation of the affected lower limb.

Material and methods of research. The results of complex examination and surgical treatment of 312 patients with purulent-necrotic complications of DFS who were hospitalised in the department of purulent surgery of Bukhara Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Centre in the period from 2017 to 2023 were analysed. All patients had different signs of severity of systemic inflammatory response syndrome. In accordance with the objectives of the study and depending on the complex treatment and methods of determining the level of amputation, the patients were conditionally divided into two groups. The first (2017-2020) group consisted of 159 (50.96%) patients, for whom the complex of surgical treatment consisted of amputations at different levels of the lower extremities for vital indications, using traditional methods before surgical

preparation. The second, main group (2021-2023) consisted of 153 (49.04%) patients who underwent amputations of lower limbs at different levels for vital indications.

Results and their discussion. Depending on the method of determining the optimal level of lower limb amputation and control of endogenous intoxication manifested as systemic inflammatory response syndrome, all 312 treated patients were conditionally divided into 2 comparable groups. At the same time, the main vital signs as well as the local status of the volume of performed surgical interventions were representative. That is, when forming the groups we observed the principle of representativeness: the parameters and volume of the lower limbs lesions and concomitant diseases were close to each other. The analysis of the degree of lower limb lesions showed that the pathological processes on the affected lower limbs in the compared groups of patients were comparable. Thus if in patients of the comparison group purulent-necrotic phlegmon was 28,2% of cases, in the main group it was observed in 28,10% of cases accordingly. Gangrene of the toes in patients of the comparison group was 40.25% of the total number of patients, while in the main group these figures were 40.52% of cases, gangrene of the distal part of the foot was observed in 21.38% and 21.57 cases, respectively. Creeping putrefactive phlegmons of the foot, carpal space and tibia accounted for 10.06% and 9.80% of cases, respectively. The analyses of comorbidities in the comparison groups were also similar, i.e. representative. It is necessary to emphasise the fact that in the comparison group of 159 patients the number of performed amputations at different levels of the lower limbs was 197 (123,9%), i.e. after primary amputation against the background of pathological process progression and wound infection we resorted to reamputation, which increased the number of operative interventions. The number of performed amputations in 153 patients of the main group was 169 (110.5%) respectively. The state of the haemostasis system in the compared groups on the background of the conducted complex of measures, in the comparative analysis we did not reveal any special reliable differences, i.e. they were comparable. The analysis of the results of surgical treatment (limb amputation) of the control group of patients showed that against the background of a complex of therapeutic measures in 38 (23.9%) patients of the study group there was a progression of both the pathological process at the level of amputation (purulent-necrotic complications) and signs of systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS). The analysis of the results of surgical treatment (limb amputation) in the main group of patients showed

that against the background of complex measures 16 (10.5%) patients of the study group showed progression of both pathological process at the level of amputation (purulent-necrotic complication) and signs of SIRS. A comparative analysis of purulent-necrotic complications that were the reason for performing lower limb reamputations at a higher level showed that while purulent-necrotic complications from the amputation stump of the fingers in the comparison group accounted for 8.8%, in the main group these complications were observed in 3.9% of patients. Progression of wound infection at the level of the foot in the comparison group was 6.3%, while in the main group of patients 3.3% of cases. Progression of the wound infection on the side of the amputation stump of the tibia in the comparison group was observed in 3,9% of patients, while these indicators in the main group of patients made up 3,3% of cases. Progression of wound infection on the side of the thigh amputation stump in the comparison group was 1.9%, in the main group such complications were not observed. The comparative analysis of the causes of fatal outcomes in the comparison groups showed that if in patients of the control group the fatal outcome was 11.95% of cases, in the patients of the main group this index significantly decreased to 3.92% of cases.

Conclusions. Application of the developed algorithm allows to radically change the stratification of amputations at one or another level, based on the implementation of the principles of routine methods of determining the expected level of truncation of the limb towards optimisation, allowing to minimise the number of unjustified high amputations from 23.9% to 10.5% and lethal outcomes from 11.95% to 3.92% of cases, respectively.

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